

A Heuristic Approach towards Continuous Implicit Authentication

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Abstract—Nowadays the vast usage of smart-phones, along with the sensitive information these could possibly contain for an individual user, raises the need for more effective and sophisticated authentication mechanisms and not only relying on the traditional ones, such as password/pattern input authentication. So there is a direction in research attempting to build machine learning models which are trained in biometric data stemming from hardware resources of the device i.e touchscreen, camera. In this paper we attempt to build an authentication process which can be employed as a biometric system. Given as input in a heuristic algorithm a series of predictions coming from machine learning models we exploit them in order to deduce a final right prediction of the identity of the user operating the device in a predetermined number of steps.

Index Terms—User Authentication, Implicit Authentication, Smartphone Security, Heuristics

I. INTRODUCTION

According to recent statistics [1], the number of mobile phone users is continuously increasing and is expected to reach the number of almost 7.5 billions, while in 2020 there were less than 7 billion users. Obviously, there is a massive turn towards mobile devices and, especially smartphones, which, nowadays, support a plethora of different every-day activities, such as work-related applications, entertainment and socializing. In that context, the mobile phones have become a valuable day-to-day assistant, with which the mobile users frequently interact. Thus, and given that many of the aforementioned applications require or handle a lot of personal data (i.e. passwords, bank accounts, photos), the privacy of the mobile owner is at high risk and the security becomes of utmost importance. The traditional authentication mechanisms, such as passwords or fingerprint, are not able to meet the current needs of increased security and are characterized by well-known limitations and deficiencies. First of all, the traditional approaches lack in terms of usability, since, according to several studies [2], [3], in an effort to refrain from remembering long and complex passwords and, instead, ensure an ease of access, users tend to disable these mechanisms [4] or select short and simple passwords or lock patterns, that are easy to memorize and recall. Furthermore, even when these authentication techniques work flawlessly, they are designed to provide a single point of entrance to the device, and, once they are passed by, they are no longer able to contain an attacker.

Towards coping with the aforementioned limitations and since the attacks are constantly becoming more sophisticated

and complex, a lot of recent research approaches are targeted towards continuous implicit authentication methodologies on the basis of behavioral biometrics. In continuous implicit authentication, data originating from the constant interaction of the mobile user with the device (e.g. taps and swipes) are used in order to provide an effective way of distinguishing the specific individual that makes use of the device. This approach does not suffer from the limitations of the traditional authentication mechanisms, since each user's interaction is being tested by the device against previously trained and constructed behavioral profiles. Additionally, the whole process is executed in the background, without affecting the user or his/her ability to operate the mobile phone.

In this context, many state-of-the-practice approaches are directed towards modelling the behavior of the users based on their interaction with the device. However, many of these approaches have from two major limitations. First of all, the experiments are usually performed in a controlled laboratory environment, with fixed conditions and parameters, which comes in contrast to the real-world usage scenarios, in which the continuous implicit authentication should be applied. Additionally, the majority of these approaches involve a limited number of users-subjects, so their generalization capability is questionable. Even without these limitations, the efficiency and the performance of many approaches is still under debate and, in many cases, it could be significantly improved.

In this work, we extend a previous methodology accomplished by Karanikiotis et al. [5], which copes with the aforementioned limitations, in order to further extend the modelling capabilities and improve its performance. We employ a parametric heuristic algorithm, which, given any continuous implicit authentication model, makes use of the model's predictions and the user gestures and, based on the short-term tendencies, updates the final predictions on the user identity. Using our approach, the correct identification of the mobile user is accomplished in a predetermined number of swipes, even when the performance of the continuous implicit authentication model is not ideal.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. Section II reviews the recent research approaches in the area of continuous implicit authentication. In Section III we present and discuss the complete methodology proposed, along with the parameter selection, while Section IV evaluates our approach in practice and against various authentication scenarios. Finally, we ana-

lyze potential threats to our internal and external validity in Section V and discuss the conclusions of our approach, along with insights for further research in Section VI.

II. RELATED WORK

III. METHODOLOGY

In this section we present the methodology we employed and is depicted in Figure 1. Applying this methodology to any given continuous implicit authentication model, for which we need to know only its performance metrics, can significantly improve the ability of the system to identify an original user or an attacker and make a correct prediction in a predefined number of swipes.

A. Authentication Algorithm

In this section we present the process we follow in order to classify a user given a series of swipes predictions. Basically, we define a decision sequence where its values are updated with the help of parametric heuristics which their logic was inferred experimentally after observing how a series of predictions containing false ones could be used in order to conclude a final right prediction. More analytically, let $s \subset \mathbb{Z}^{0+}$ represent the indexing of the swipes and p_s the sequence of predictions of given swipes which its value range is the two elements set $\{-1, 1\}$. Also, we define the important set $W = \{3w + 1 : w \in s\}$ which basically represents an indexing of the swipes with a step of length three. The reason for the choice of length three will be clarified later on this subsection. Then we can define the decision sequence which consists of a pair of two strictly positive parameters (a, b) as follows:

$$D_{s+1} = \begin{cases} D_s - a(2^{-fs}) + \frac{b}{2}I\{P\}e^{-s+1}, & \text{if } p_s = -1 \\ D_s + b(2^{-fs}) - \frac{a}{2}I\{Q\}e^{-s+1}, & \text{if } p_s = 1 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

,where $I\{*\}$ represents the indicator function and it gives the value of 1 when the condition inside the brackets is satisfied and 0 otherwise and the arguments of I are two logical statements as $P = (D_{s+1} < D_s < D_{s-1} : s \in W)$ and $Q = (D_{s+1} > D_s > D_{s-1} : s \in W)$. The decision sequence consists of two important terms which essentially define the parametric heuristics mentioned in the beginning. The first one is the *update term* which is in one case $-a(2^{-fs})$ and the other $b(2^{-fs})$ and is responsible for increasing or decreasing the value of the sequence based on the prediction p_s . The contribution of this term slowly vanishes, in order to obtain fast decisions and to avoid long term sudden changes. The parameter f is just a constant given a fixed value of order 10^{-3} to ensure a slowly vanishing term. The second one is the *confirmation term*, i.e. $\frac{b}{2}I\{P\}e^{-s+1}$ and $-\frac{a}{2}I\{Q\}e^{-s+1}$ which essentially changes the value of the sequence in the opposite direction when two consecutive decreases or increases are observed. The idea behind this term is to avoid quick false decisions based on the occurrence of false predictions. The contribution of this term decreases exponentially and after some terms is considered negligible. The confirmation term takes place every three swipes, since it is based on the set

W , and only if the logical statements P, Q are satisfied in this positions. The reason for the three length step of W is because we want to avoid having confirmations happening continuously and thus hindering the contribution of the updating term. Also, we want the confirmation term to occur due to consecutive increases or decreases only from the update terms and not from previous confirmation terms since the P and Q look out to the two previous values of decision sequence. Then we choose an initial value D_0 for the sequence. The final decision is made by choosing two border values D_{low} and D_{high} , such that $D_{low} \leq D_0 \leq D_{high}$, and if the value of the sequence at some point surpasses the D_{high} value, i.e. $D_{s+1} \geq D_{high}$, then the final prediction is that the swipes belong to the original user, otherwise if $D_{s+1} \leq D_{low}$ at some point then the swipes belong to an attacker. The pseudocode for the algorithm is given in (Algorithm 1). Furthermore, there exist two important conditions governing the parameters (a, b) , except being positive. The first one is derived by the fact that we do not want the algorithm to terminate in one step, i.e. $D_1 \geq D_{high}$ or $D_1 \leq D_{low}$, because that could lead to a false decision due to a possible misprediction positioned at first and also the confirmation term will never take place, since it needs at least two previous realizations of the sequence. The condition is given as

$$a < D_0 - D_{low} \quad (2)$$

$$b < D_{high} - D_0$$

The second condition ensures that the algorithm will not terminate, i.e. surpass a border value, after a confirmation term. Because then the confirmation is going to lose its meaning and its function in the logic of the algorithm. Namely the conditions is given as

$$\frac{4(D_{low} - D_0)}{3 + 2^{1-f}} < b - a < \frac{4(D_{high} - D_0)}{3 + 2^{1-f}} \quad (3)$$

The derivations of these inequalities can be found in the Appendix A

B. Probabilistic Analysis and Parameter Computation

The input to our algorithm is probabilistic since a machine learning classification model makes false or correct predictions. Also we do not possess information for the moment of a right or a false prediction occurrence. But by the frequentist view, considering that we tested our machine learning model in a big number of swipes, we can estimate the probability of having a false prediction. Specifically, the probability of false prediction has two different values for two different cases. The first one is the case where the predictions are made from the original user's swipes and the probability is given by:

$$FRR = \frac{\text{original user rejected swipes}}{\text{original user total swipes}} \quad (4)$$

And the second one is the case where the predictions are from the attacker's swipes with false prediction probability:

$$FAR = \frac{\text{attacker accepted swipes}}{\text{attacker total swipes}} \quad (5)$$

Fig. 1. Our system methodology pipeline

Algorithm 1 Decision Sequence(p_s)

```

1: for  $s$  in  $0 \dots \text{length}(p_s)$  do
2:   if  $p_s = -1$  then
3:      $D_{s+1} \leftarrow D_s - a \cdot 2^{-fs}$ 
4:     if  $s \in W$  and  $D_{s+1} < D_s < D_{s-1}$  then
5:        $D_{s+1} \leftarrow D_{s+1} + \frac{b}{2} \cdot e^{-s+1}$ 
6:     end if
7:   else
8:      $D_{s+1} \leftarrow D_s + b \cdot 2^{-fs}$ 
9:     if  $s \in W$  and  $D_{s+1} > D_s > D_{s-1}$  then
10:       $D_{s+1} \leftarrow D_{s+1} - \frac{a}{2} \cdot e^{-s+1}$ 
11:    end if
12:   end if
13:   if  $D_{s+1} \geq D_{high}$  then
14:     Original user identified!
15:     break
16:   end if
17:   if  $D_{s+1} \leq D_{low}$  then
18:     Attacker identified!
19:     break
20:   end if
21: end for

```

So, now we are able to analyze the behavior of our algorithm in two separate cases. The first one is when the algorithm is getting as input a series of predictions from the user's swipes and the second one is the case where is getting input from an attacker.

1) *User case*: Since FRR (4) is the estimated probability of having a false prediction on the original user swipes, i.e. the probability that the prediction p_s takes the value of -1 on a swipe s , we can define two sets of random variables which are related with the update and confirmation terms in every swipe. Since the swipes are considered independent from each other the random variables are also independent. Specifically let

$$U_s = \begin{cases} b, & 1 - FRR \\ -a, & FRR \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

be the identical and independent random variables associated with the update term in every swipe s which has the form of

scaled bernoulli trials. And

$$C_s = \begin{cases} -\frac{a}{2}, & (1 - FRR) \cdot (1 - FRR) \\ \frac{b}{2}, & FRR \cdot FRR \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

be the i.i.d random variables associated with the confirmation term which has the form of two scaled independent consecutive bernoulli trials. Since the expression of the decision sequence (8) depends on the realization of the prediction p_s , we can rewrite it in terms of the random variables we declared above, as follows:

$$D_{s+1} = D_s + U_s \cdot 2^{-fs} + C_w \cdot e^{-w+1} \quad (8)$$

where $w \in W$. Now we can compute the decision sequence after k swipes in function of the initial value D_0 . The formula occurs by induction as:

$$D_k = D_0 + \sum_{s=0}^{k-1} U_s \cdot T_s + \sum_{s \in W} C_s \cdot e^{-s+1} \quad (9)$$

where $T_s = 2^{-fs}$. The reason for the above formulation of the decision sequence is that now we are able to compute the expected value of it after k swipes, which yields

$$E[D_k] = D_0 - G \cdot E[U_s] + N \cdot E[C_s] \quad (10)$$

where G is the result of the geometric series $\sum T_s$ and N is an exponent sum, with their exact expressions presented in Appendix B together with the derivations of all the above results. After the expected value has been computed we desire it to be greater than or equal to D_{high} because in the case of $D_k \geq D_{high}$ the algorithm will decide that the swipes belong to the original user.

2) *Attacker case*: Similarly in the case of an attacker FAR is the estimated probability of having a false prediction. Respectively we define similar i.i.d random variables related with the terms in the decision sequence in every swipe. Namely let

$$A_s = \begin{cases} -a, & 1 - FAR \\ b, & FAR \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

be associated with the update term. And

$$V_s = \begin{cases} \frac{b}{2}, & (1 - FAR) \cdot (1 - FAR) \\ -\frac{a}{2}, & FAR \cdot FAR \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

be associated with the confirmation term. In a similar fashion the expression for the decision sequence takes the form of the random variable:

$$D_{s+1} = D_s + A_s \cdot 2^{-f_s} + V_w \cdot e^{-w+1} \quad (13)$$

where $w \in W$. In order to evaluate the expected value after k swipes, we follow the same procedure as before with the difference that in the case of the random variable we substitute U_s with A_s and C_s with V_s . The expression is

$$E[D_k] = D_0 - G \cdot E[A_s] + N \cdot E[V_s] \quad (14)$$

In this case we desire the expected value to be less than or equal to D_{low} because if $D_k \leq D_{low}$ the algorithm decides that the swipes belong to the attacker.

Our goal is to calculate the parameter pair (a, b) for every user. So by letting $E[D_k] = D_{high}$ in the user's case and $E[D_k] = D_{low}$ in attacker's case we are able to create a 2×2 linear system of the form $Ax = d$ where $x = [a, b]^T$. Since we got the exact expressions for $E[D_k]$ in each case, with simple calculations we can derive the formulation of the linear system. By letting a function $f: \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ as $f(x) = x \cdot G + \frac{N}{2} \cdot (1-x)^2$ the explicit form of the system is:

$$\begin{bmatrix} -f(FRR) & f(1 - FRR) \\ -f(1 - FAR) & f(FAR) \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} a \\ b \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} D_{high} - D_0 \\ D_{low} - D_0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (15)$$

So, we have the ability to compute the vector x in an inexpensive way, since we are dealing with a linear system in matrix form and lots of computer algebra systems exist for solving this efficiently. But, the solution vector will still be a function of G , i.e. $x = [a(G), b(G)]^T$. So, we can choose a value for k_{th} swipe we desire the process to terminate and easily transform it to the value G with the equation (20) in Appendix B and plug it in the solution vector to obtain the parameter pair (a, b) . Also naturally this linear system has a condition of the existence of the solution which is provided from the determinant of A matrix. Since the FAR, FRR values are in the range $[0, 1]$ the only condition that applies is the obvious one $FAR + FRR \neq 1$. In practise the condition is not an obstacle in the search of solutions since the models satisfying this condition are impractical and not used. The general scheme of the system is depicted in ??.

IV. EVALUATION

In this section we present the results of experiments conducted to test the methodology of this paper. Initially, from the dataset [6] we extract data from twenty users in total with a sufficient number of swipes in order to obtain a better estimation of the misprediction probabilities and also to conduct as many experiments as possible. Based on the results of FAR, FRR we choose the k_{th} swipe that the algorithm will

terminate. We let $D_0 = 0.55$, $D_{high} = 0.8$ and $D_{low} = 0.3$. These values were chosen so that $|D_0 - D_{low}| = |D_0 - D_{high}|$ in order to ensure fairness in the decision sequence. Also, the conditions (2,3) simplify. Then we divide the series of predictions into smaller segments which we will refer as sessions in order to simulate a real life scenario where someone makes a use of a phone in order to complete a particular task. Approximately, we consider the number of swipes required for completing a task in a smart phone is about 15 to 20, so the sessions will consist of twenty swipes for every experiment. The metric that we use for the evaluation is the percentage of sessions in which we correctly identify the user. The evaluation process has the following three stages.

A. Models Evaluation

In the first stage we employ a sample machine learning model for novelty detection, namely a Local Outlier Factor(LOF), and present the results of the algorithm in I and also we make use of other machine learning models as base models in order to show the independence of our methodology regarding the underlying model. Namely, the models are an Autoencoder for novelty detection and an ensemble model with One-Class Support Vector Machines combined with LOFs, their respective results are presented in II. In the first three columns is the indexing of the users, the FAR and FRR metrics. The column \hat{k} represents the estimated number of the swipes we chose in order for the algorithm to terminate. The k_U, k_A columns are the actual mean number of swipes of the sessions that the algorithm terminated for the user and attacker respectively. The $U(\%), A(\%)$ columns are the percentages of the sessions in which the algorithm correctly identified the user and attacker respectively. Finally, the last column $\#Exps_{U/A}$ represents the number of experiments conducted, specifically the left hand side of the slash(/) is the number of experiments for the user while the right is the number for the attackers.

TABLE I
LOCAL OUTLIER FACTOR

ID	FAR	FRR	k	k	k	U	A	Ex
1	0.46	0.15	8	8.27	7.48	96.6	87.64	30/1190
2	0.12	0.12	4	4.86	5.03	100	99.75	15/1205
3	0.28	0.15	5	6.15	5.7	100	97.59	13/1207
4	0.44	0.11	8	8.36	7.93	100	91.48	11/1209
5	0.52	0.16	8	8.1	6.33	90	86.61	10/1210
6	0.25	0.15	6	6.3	6.47	100	98.4	10/1210
7	0.45	0.16	6	6.6	5.15	90	87.19	10/1210
8	0.35	0.16	5	4.75	5.5	88.8	94.13	9/1211
9	0.34	0.14	6	5.88	6.51	100	97.27	9/1211
10	0.21	0.15	5	4.88	5.87	100	99.42	9/1211
11	0.55	0.12	10	10.09	8.01	91.3	83.56	23/919
12	0.57	0.12	10	9.3	7.79	90.9	82.39	22/920
13	0.37	0.12	8	8.82	7.97	100	94.7	17/925
14	0.26	0.14	7	7.25	7.48	100	97.19	16/926
15	0.4	0.14	8	7.61	7.48	100	92.35	13/929
16	0.4	0.15	7	7.16	6.73	100	91.82	12/930
17	0.41	0.17	8	7.91	7.48	100	91	12/930
18	0.41	0.1	7	6.09	7.2	100	89.68	11/931
19	0.43	0.16	9	10.09	8.29	100	89.9	11/931
20	0.07	0.16	5	5.8	5.75	100	100	10/931

As we can see from I the maximum deviation from the expected number of swipes is 2.21 which happens in the user with ID 12 who has the worst prediction capability since its pair of FAR, FRR metrics is very high, specifically FAR is equal to 57%. Generally, when the pair of FAR, FRR is getting lower the deviation also decreases. For instance, the user with ID 20 has very satisfying FAR, FRR metrics and its deviation from the expected number of swipes is less than one and its success rate is perfect in both cases. Furthermore the user success rate in most cases is ideal but for this result also plays role the fact that the number of experiments for the users is small in comparison with that of the attackers which is huge. Finally, we observe that for a mediocre model such as the user with ID 3 has very satisfying results, namely 100% success rate in the user experiments and 97.59% in the attacker experiments. In II we employed an Autoencoder for the users with the ID 1 to 8 and ensembling learning with Local Outlier Factors models and One-Class Support Vector Machines models for the rest.

TABLE II
AUTOENCODER-ENSEMBLE

ID	FAR	FRR	k	k	U	A	Exps
1	0.38	0.06	7	7.46	7.79	100	96.76 15/1205
2	0.67	0.08	7	7.5	5.2	88.88	75.14 9/1211
3	0.53	0.16	9	7.22	7.17	100	82.98 9/1211
4	0.54	0.14	8	7.77	6.61	95.65	84.65 23/919
5	0.68	0.07	7	7.31	5.93	86.36	77.6 22/920
6	0.66	0.09	8	7.84	5.68	100	77.6 13/929
7	0.7	0.07	8	7.1	5.88	90.9	77.87 11/931
8	0.09	0.10	4	4.4	4.64	100	100 10/931
9	0.14	0.02	5	5	5.56	100	100 15/1205
10	0.29	0.03	5	5	5.78	100	99.33 9/1211
11	0.02	0.03	4	4.6	4.16	100	100 10/931

Initially, in II some users are missing due to the fact that for their particular FAR, FRR metrics the conditions 2,3 are not met since the values of the metrics are very high. In general we let the Autoencoder to be a non efficient model, in particular it is biased towards the positive predictions(user). So we observe while the FRR metric is very low the user percentage of success is also affected since a good model is defined by having both FAR, FRR metrics low. Furthermore, we employed a collection of classifiers, as mentioned above, in order to construct very efficient models and as we can see in this case correct identification is achieved in every session.

B. Model Efficiency Improvement

In the first stage the main evaluation metric of our methodology is the percentage of the sessions in which the algorithm correctly identified the user, both in the case of an attacker and the original user. These success rate metrics can be transformed back again to FAR and FRR metrics. Specifically, our methodology in the experiments makes predictions in every session, which consists of twenty swipes. So, in the case of the original user if a session does not recognize him as the user or recognizes him as attacker then the prediction in this session is false. Respectively, in the case of an attacker, the prediction in a session is considered false, if in these twenty

swipes the algorithm does not recognize him. Thus, we can extend the FAR and FRR metrics, by letting the predictions to be represented by the final prediction in a session. Analytically, the FAR metric equals the quantity $100 - A(\%)$ and the FRR metric is $100 - U(\%)$. The main goal of this paper is to effectively enhance the prediction capability of the machine learning models. In order to show the improvement of the efficiency this methodology achieves, we make plots from the data of table I, which are the output of Local Outlier Factor model and the new results in comparison with the initial ones are depicted below. Figure 2 depicts the improvement of the FAR metric and figure 3 depicts the improvement of FRR.

Fig. 2. FAR Improvement

Fig. 3. FRR Improvement

We measure the improvement quantitatively as the mean absolute difference \bar{d} of the data points in 2,3. The improvement in the FAR metric is $\bar{d} = 29\%$ while in FRR is $\bar{d} = 11\%$. The reason for the lesser improvement in FRR is the fact that the initial values are already low in the scale of 10 – 20%.

In table III we include the mean FAR,FRR metrics computed in our experiments from the authentication algorithm with the final results of the same metrics of models created in other related studies. The mean of the metrics comes from

I where the base model is just a sample Local Outlier Factor model.

TABLE III
COMPARISON TO OTHER STUDIES

Approach	FAR	FRR	# of Subjects
Yang et al. [7]	15%	8%	200
Draffin et al. [8]	14%	2.2%	13
Feng et al. [9]	9%	7%	23
Shen et al. [10]	5.01%	6.85%	48
Lee et al. [11]	2.8%	0.09%	35
Karanikiotis et al. [12]	-	4.7-5.7%	2,221
Ours with sample model	7.39%	2.62%	20

As can be seen from III our approach achieves very satisfying results also in comparison with other related studies and given the fact that the focus of this study is not to construct an efficient machine learning model, the results of III occurred from a sample untuned model. Obviously, if the base model is replaced with a better model the final results will also be outstandingly improved.

C. Frequency of Attacker Accepted Swipes

In the first stage we considered the mean number of swipes that the algorithm terminated in the experiments among the sessions. In this stage, we present the explicit distribution of the attackers swipes for 4 users from I with IDs $\{2, 3, 11, 20\}$ where their corresponding FAR, FRR are depicted as labels in the histogram

Fig. 4. Histograms of Attackers Swipes

The top two histograms in Figure 4, which belong to users with satisfying FAR, FRR have heavy left tail which is a positive result since almost $\sim 80\%$ of the attackers has completed less than 5 swipes. In the bottom two histograms in which FAR, FRR are not satisfying but still most of the attackers are distributed in the lowest number of swipes.

Following, we explicitly present in table IV the exact frequencies of the accepted attacker swipes for all the users from I to show that the most attackers were recognized in less than six swipes.

TABLE IV
FREQUENCY OF ATTACKER ACCEPTED SWIPES

Number of swipes	Frequency
≤ 6	11,678
7-9	3,734
> 9	4,403

We acknowledged that a potential attacker in a real scenario will not be able to cause any harm in less than six swipes using the smartphone. So the results of IV are very satisfying, since explicitly quantify the total number of accepted swipes across all the attackers and the overall tendency is that the attackers are recognized from the algorithm in a small number of swipes.

V. THREATS TO VALIDITY

VI. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper we attempted to identify the imposter and the user of a smartphone device based on a sequence of swipes and experiments were conducted for a variety of FAR and FRR metrics on purpose in order to show that our methodology is efficient even for mediocre models. Specifically, we achieve more than 90% success rate even for a model with FAR $\sim 40\%$. As a future work we can consider also the variance of the decision sequence in both cases and attempt to minimize it and compute the parameters. Also then we will be able to study the concentration bounds of the sequence and thus ensure a better convergence to the expected behaviour. But this approach adds a lot of complexity to the system since variances create non-linear equations and finding a common solution is a cumbersome task also without simple guarantees or conditions for the existence of such solution.

APPENDIX A

We want the decision sequence to satisfy $D_{low} < D_1 < D_{high}$. We have two possible realizations of the term D_1 that is why we derive and two inequalities. For the first one, let $p_0 = -1$ then

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_{low} < D_1 < D_{high} &\Rightarrow D_{low} < D_0 - a < D_{high} \\
 &\Rightarrow D_{low} - D_0 < -a < D_{high} - D_0 \\
 &\Rightarrow D_0 - D_{high} < a < D_0 - D_{low}
 \end{aligned}$$

Since $a > 0$ and $D_0 < D_{high}$ we are only keeping the left hand side inequality, so the first condition is derived. In a similar way, if $p_0 = 1$ then

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_{low} < D_1 < D_{high} &\Rightarrow D_{low} < D_0 + b < D_{high} \\
 &\Rightarrow D_{low} - D_0 < b < D_{high} - D_0 \\
 &\Rightarrow D_{low} - D_0 < b < D_{high} - D_0
 \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, $b > 0$ and $D_{low} < D_0$ we keep only the right hand side inequality.

The confirmation terms should not force the decision sequence to terminate the algorithm. We begin by constraining the first confirmation and then we will show that it is sufficient

for constraining the rest. In the first case we assume that $p_0 = -1$ and $p_1 = -1$ then

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{low} &< D_2 < D_{high} \Rightarrow \\
&\Rightarrow D_{low} < D_0 - a - a \cdot 2^{-f} + \frac{b}{2} < D_{high} \\
&\Rightarrow D_{low} - D_0 < \frac{b}{2} - a \cdot (1 + 2^{-f}) < D_{high} - D_0 \\
&\Rightarrow 2 \cdot (D_{low} - D_0) < b - a \cdot (2 + 2^{1-f}) < 2 \cdot (D_{high} - D_0)
\end{aligned} \tag{16}$$

In the case where $p_0 = 1$ and $p_1 = 1$ we derive

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{low} &< D_2 < D_{high} \Rightarrow \\
&\Rightarrow D_{low} < D_0 + b + b \cdot 2^{-f} - \frac{a}{2} < D_{high} \\
&\Rightarrow D_{low} - D_0 < -\frac{a}{2} + b \cdot (1 + 2^{-f}) < D_{high} - D_0 \\
&\Rightarrow 2 \cdot (D_{low} - D_0) < b \cdot (2 + 2^{1-f}) - a < 2 \cdot (D_{high} - D_0)
\end{aligned} \tag{17}$$

By summing (16) and (17) we have

$$\frac{4(D_{low} - D_0)}{3 + 2^{1-f}} < b - a < \frac{4(D_{high} - D_0)}{3 + 2^{1-f}} \tag{18}$$

APPENDIX B

Initially we need to find an expression for the decision sequence after k in function with the constant initial value D_0 to easily calculate the expected value afterwards. So, by computing inductively the sequence (8) we have:

$$\begin{aligned}
D_1 &= D_0 + U_0 \cdot T_0 \\
D_2 &= D_1 + U_1 \cdot T_1 + C_1 \\
&\dots \\
D_k &= D_0 + \sum_{s=0}^{k-1} U_s \cdot T_s + \sum_{s \in W} C_s \cdot e^{-s+1}
\end{aligned}$$

In order to calculate the expected value we take the expectation operator in equation (9).

$$E[D_k] = E[D_0 + \sum_{s=0}^{k-1} U_s \cdot T_s + \sum_{s \in W} C_s \cdot e^{-s+1}]$$

By the linearity of expected value operator

$$\begin{aligned}
E[D_k] &= E[D_0] + E[\sum_{s=0}^{k-1} U_s \cdot T_s] + E[\sum_{s \in W} C_s \cdot e^{-s+1}] \\
&= D_0 + \sum_{s=0}^{k-1} E[U_s \cdot T_s] + \sum_{s \in W} E[C_s \cdot e^{-s+1}] \\
&= D_0 + E[U_s] \cdot \sum_{s=0}^{k-1} T_s + E[C_s] \cdot \sum_{s \in W} e^{-s+1}
\end{aligned} \tag{19}$$

Considering that $T_s = 2^{-fs}$ the sum $G = \sum T_s$ in equation (19) is a geometric series of the form $\sum_{k=0}^n ar^k$ with $a = 1$ and $r = 2^{-f}$ without the last element. So to calculate G :

$$\begin{aligned}
\sum_{s=0}^{k-1} 2^{-fs} &= \frac{1 - 2^{-fk}}{1 - 2^{-f}} \Rightarrow \\
G &= \frac{1 - 2^{-fk}}{1 - 2^{-f}}
\end{aligned} \tag{20}$$

Also in equation the term $N = \sum_{s \in W} e^{-s+1}$ is an exponent sum indexed with the set W which represents integers with a jump of three. The terms of the sum are approaching zero very fast so in our computations we consider only the first three terms and N takes the form $N = 1 + e^{-3} + e^{-6}$. Finally the equation (19) yields (14).

REFERENCES

- [1] "Forecast number of mobile devices worldwide from 2020 to 2025," <https://www.statista.com/statistics/218984/number-of-global-mobile-users-since-2010/>, 2021, [Online; accessed March-2022].
- [2] E. Chin, A. P. Felt, V. Sekar, and D. Wagner, "Measuring user confidence in smartphone security and privacy," in *Proceedings of the Eighth Symposium on Usable Privacy and Security*, ser. SOUPS '12. New York, NY, USA: Association for Computing Machinery, 2012. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1145/2335356.2335358>
- [3] W. Melicher, M. Mazurek, D. Kurilova, S. Segreti, P. Kalvani, R. Shay, B. Ur, L. Bauer, N. Christin, and L. Cranor, "Usability and security of text passwords on mobile devices," 05 2016, pp. 527–539.
- [4] S. Egelman, S. Jain, R. S. Portnoff, K. Liao, S. Consolvo, and D. Wagner, "Are you ready to lock?" in *Proceedings of the 2014 ACM SIGSAC Conference on Computer and Communications Security*, ser. CCS '14. New York, NY, USA: Association for Computing Machinery, 2014, p. 750–761. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1145/2660267.2660273>
- [5] T. Karanikiotis, M. D. Papamichail, K. C. Chatzidimitriou, N.-C. I. Oikonomou, A. L. Symeonidis, and S. K. Saripalle, "Continuous implicit authentication through touch traces modelling," in *2020 IEEE 20th International Conference on Software Quality, Reliability and Security (QRS)*, 2020, pp. 111–120.
- [6] M. D. Papamichail, K. C. Chatzidimitriou, T. Karanikiotis, N.-C. I. Oikonomou, A. L. Symeonidis, and S. K. Saripalle, "Brainrun: A behavioral biometrics dataset towards continuous implicit authentication," *Data*, vol. 4, no. 2, p. 60, 2019.
- [7] L. Yang, Y. Guo, X. Ding, J. Han, Y. Liu, C. Wang, and C. Hu, "Unlocking smart phone through handwaving biometrics," *IEEE Transactions on Mobile Computing*, vol. 14, no. 5, pp. 1044–1055, 2014.
- [8] B. Draffin, J. Zhu, and J. Zhang, "Keysens: Passive user authentication through micro-behavior modeling of soft keyboard interaction," in *International Conference on Mobile Computing, Applications, and Services*. Springer, 2013, pp. 184–201.
- [9] T. Feng, Z. Liu, K.-A. Kwon, W. Shi, B. Carbutar, Y. Jiang, and N. Nguyen, "Continuous mobile authentication using touchscreen gestures," in *2012 IEEE conference on technologies for homeland security (HST)*. IEEE, 2012, pp. 451–456.
- [10] C. Shen, T. Yu, S. Yuan, Y. Li, and X. Guan, "Performance analysis of motion-sensor behavior for user authentication on smartphones," *Sensors*, vol. 16, no. 3, p. 345, 2016.
- [11] W.-H. Lee and R. B. Lee, "Sensor-based implicit authentication of smartphone users," in *2017 47th Annual IEEE/IFIP International Conference on Dependable Systems and Networks (DSN)*. IEEE, 2017, pp. 309–320.
- [12] T. Karanikiotis, M. D. Papamichail, K. C. Chatzidimitriou, N.-C. I. Oikonomou, A. L. Symeonidis, and S. K. Saripalle, "Continuous implicit authentication through touch traces modelling," in *2020 IEEE 20th International Conference on Software Quality, Reliability and Security (QRS)*. IEEE, 2020, pp. 111–120.